

Social Change and its effects on Generation Gap in the Pashtun Society of Balochistan

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Mr. Muhammad Rahim

Lecturer Sociology, Department of Sociology, University of Balochistan, Quetta.

Email: rahimnasar83@gmail.com

Dr. Muhammad Alam Tareen

Professor, Sociology and Dean Social Sciences, University of Balochistan, Quetta.

Email: dralamtareen@gmail.com

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Abstract

The generation gap is the discrepancies between the old and young generations regarding their views, thoughts, lifestyle, experiences, ambitions, knowledge, dreams, values, and different other aspects of social life. This cleavage is natural as well adopted especially by the young generation because the social world is changing very rapidly, the said generation desires and trying to move with this change, but the old generation is not that open and often proved stubborn to adopt the new ways of life. So, as a result, a gap creates between the two generations, which later causes conflict and distances between these generations. This research paper evaluates the understanding and knowledge of the old generation about the generation gap and the state of actions and interactions in the generation gap among Pashtuns in Balochistan. In this quantitative research study, the data were collected from people above the age of fifty years from the Zhob division through proportionate random sampling, with a sample size of 200 respondents. The primary data was gathered through an interview schedule, in which the majority of the respondents communicated that a generation gap exists in their community which suffers more from the old generation. They complained that children are not cooperative and remain at distance from parents in different spheres of life, which seriously affect the relationship between the two age groups. The study informs that the old generation requires to develop a flexible and smooth relationship with the young generation to strengthen human development.

Keywords: Actions; Interactions; Generation Gap; Old Generation; Parents.

Introduction

Generation gap is the differences in mindsets of one generation from the other in respect of attitudes, norms, values, beliefs, behaviors, assumptions, dreams, perceptions, reflections, etc. Oxford dictionary explains the generation gap, that it is the failure or inability of the young generation and the old ones to develop a mutual understanding (Buheji, 2019). These differences in social and cultural life between the younger generation and their elders occur when the two generations don't understand each other because of their different life

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experiences, habits, behavior, and opinions (Dunning, 2007). The generational gap usually occurs when there is a communication gap regarding value transmission between the two conflicting generations. This type of discrepancies and values mismatch comes forth due to different life experiences of the new and old generations. Through the generational gap, the young generation is going to change their reference group other than their parents inside the families, which as a result harms the relationship between the two generations in the household. The generation gap is emerged due to socio-economic and political differences or the influence and sudden change in lifestyle of the modern period (Woodman & Wyn, 2015). intergenerational dissonance emerges when youth transit into adulthood. For him, this gap is sometimes natural but other times it is done deliberately, which can be seen everywhere in interactions at restaurants, markets, sports clubs, and other activity centers (Cochrane et al., 2016).

The issues of generations and generation gap came into discussion in the twentieth century as a dynamic topic with the generation defined by the natural existence, familial relations, and the people's relations and interactions with other social beings. The major focus remained on youth in the past century. It is because the young generation had a sharp experience of the rapidly changing world in western societies until the 1970s, regarding their distinct role in the revival of social and cultural traits after the devastating two world wars. This took a special interest in the generation of 1914 after world war first and baby boomers after World War second (Bristow, 2015). Baby boomers are the generation born between (1946-1964) for the first time showing a wide gap in ideas, values, and views with their parents (Esler, 1984; Sutor et al., 1995; Lye, 1996; Dhiman & Jain, 2016). The people were more conscious about knowing the causes and issues of generational diversity, which used to lead society towards social change, change in values, and lifestyle. The cleavage widened the gap between the young and old generations regarding diverse ideas. Many studies since the existence of this gap found that the generational gap has caused physical isolation, which has led to mental isolation between the two generations, which has resulted in weak communication or communication barrier across the two age groups (Troll, 1972). Experts believe that the phenomenon of the generational gap has not been a very serious issue in the past until the emergence of modern industrial society; particularly, before the 20th century, there was no evident sign of this gap and conflict, as manifested in the form of rebellion and continuous confrontation between the young and old generations in today's world (Milkman, 2017).

The generation gap is a communication failure, which leads the two age groups to intergenerational conflict. The parents are usually mature in the sense that they don't show sympathy for the transforming moral principles and way of thinking in contemporary society (Dhiman & Jain, 2016). It is plain to see why parents and their teenagers often clash. They don't understand each other and worse than that, they don't respect each other. Adolescents threaten the authority of parents, educators, and traditional institutions. According to social control theory (Hirschi, 1995), the detachment of young persons from parents and community institutions of conventional society weakens social control over them. In its moderate mode, the conflict is a generation gap and in its extreme mode, it is a generation of war (Chen et al., 2003).

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Objectives of the study

- To see the knowledge and understanding of parents about the generation gap.
- To know the actions and interactions within the family and parents' behavior towards children.

Review of the Literature

In intergenerational discrepancies, the two generations usually live in different socio-cultural environments and experience different cultural standards, influenced by different styles of living, media, technology, customs, beliefs, norms, and values. Therefore, the generation gap is naturally a cultural gap, which distinguishes one generation from the other. Today computers, the internet, and other technology have made society very complex, which cannot be fully understood by the older generation. Meanwhile, they want to maintain the status quo, which is quite difficult for the youngsters to follow, which as a result promotes generational dissonance. A Peer group is the forum that usually molds the behavior, attitude, and conduct of the individual, particularly adolescents. The youth most often spend their time with peer groups. In urban areas, this group enables the child to develop autonomous behavior and emancipation from the dominating influence of parents (Patil, 2014). The generation gap is a worldwide phenomenon. It is universal and continual (Welty, 1991). A generation at first attacked its elders, now that same generation faces off their juniors (Strutton, Pelton, & Ferrell, 1997). The generational gap is a reality, this gap or discrepancies can never be disappeared completely (Vassi et al., 2008). It is further argued that the generation gap is not only a reality but a sea-change in human history (Mead, 1971). In this process, both parent and child are equally responsible for contributing to these differences. Many researchers have shown specific interest in the parent-child conflict on the emotions and behavioral problems throughout the developmental stages of the child (Vassi et al., 2008).

The sources of generational division were expressed through culture – in fashion, music, media and leisure, and social outlook, and this was facilitated by rapid economic and technological change. The economic and technological changes that gathered and expedited after the Second World War, impacted most strata in society and sustained for much longer and resulted in the rise of mass consumerism, mass culture, and mass affluence (Higgs & Gilleard, 2010).

Scholars examined the extent to which early family experiences contribute to variation in social interaction, affective closeness, and the exchange of help between parents and children. They found that greater intimacy and a tighter bond in relations between parents and adult children were related to a higher level of affection and acceptance during childhood, a stronger sense of family cohesion, and closer parent-child relations during adolescence. They concluded that intergenerational relations are primarily the result of a "snowball" effect, with the qualities of early parent-child relationships continuing to symbolize relations into the children's adulthood. So, it is therefore expected that parent-child relationships in adulthood will be related to the parent-child and other family relationships of childhood. Adult children's marital quality may be shaped both by early family experiences and parent-child relationships and by existing intergenerational relationships (Shapiro, 2004). The link between parent-child relationships in childhood and intimate relationships in adulthood has been the focus of several theoretical frameworks, including psychoanalytic theory (Freud,

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1949), life-span developmental approach (Baltes & Reese, 1984), attribution theory (Kelley, 1972), attachment theory (Bowlby, 1979) and intergenerational theory (Tuason & Friedlander, 2000). Psychoanalytic and object relations theorists have long argued that the parent-child relationship is the prototype for later love relationships. Similarly, attachment theory posits that working models of childhood attachment relationships are strongly related to the quality of couple relationships in adulthood (Bowlby, 1979; Lavee, et al, 2005).

Baumrind (1991) finds a comprehensive categorization, in which parental styles are categorized into three groups: authoritarian, authoritative, and permissive. Authoritarian parents expect indisputable obedience and exchange of thoughts without flexibility. These parents are not responsive and show no intimacy with their children. Reinforcement theory emphasizes that reinforcing positive behavioral aspects spreads the acceptance inclination of parents and parents' strictness leads to the acceptance of their message because of forming negative emotional states. Authoritative parents impose severe controls on their children's behaviors; at the same time, they listen to their children's ideas and even judge according to their behaviors. They feel responsible for their children, have clear and high expectations, and guide their behaviors. So, according to attachment theory, the children who are more attached to their parents in terms of security are more inclined to accept their beliefs and values. But permissive parents have few expectations and low training supervision. They are intimate and responsive; but they do not have clear expectations and do not guide their children's behaviors (Grusec & Goodnow., 1994; Tanaka, Okagaki, & Miura-Mattausch, 1999). As relatively experienced members of our respective professions, we perceive that younger people tend to be particularly ignorant or dismissive about ethical dilemmas when they involve the management of information and its associated technology. A fellow professor studying the one-child policy in mainland China recently expressed a similar concern that those born after 1980 have any sense of shame or respect. Others portray the younger generation in China as self-centered and pampered (Rosenzweig & Zhang, 2009; Martinsons & Ma, 2009). Elders in societies throughout the ages are likely to have held similar viewpoints. However, specific concerns about the ethics of the younger generation in China have been reinforced by the following: thefts of intellectual property by technicians repairing computing equipment under the supervision of young managers and widespread cheating on college entrance exams as well as many other educational tests (Martinsons & Ma, 2009).

Material and Method

The study was carried out through the positivistic approach of sociology, where a quantitative research method was employed to conduct this research study. The locale for the study was the Zhob division, where this study focused on three districts of the division including Loralai, Killa Saifullah, and Zhob, in which the data was collected from the old generations, and only those male individuals were made the part of the sample who were more than fifty years old. The data was collected through the probability sampling technique. To draw a representative sampling from the universe, it was at first divided into three districts of Zhob, Killa Saifullah, and Loralai, later a sample was drawn through proportionate random sampling. The sample size for the study was 200 male respondents, where 60 respondents were selected from district Zhob, 65 respondents from district Killa Saifullah and 75 respondents were selected from district Loralai. The interview schedule was used as

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a tool for data collection. The data was further analyzed through SPSS.

Data Analysis and Discussions

The generation gap is a universal phenomenon. No society in the world is spare, however, its magnitude may be varied from society to society because of its cultural, normative, actions, and interaction mode. This gap usually occurs when the old generation rests unfamiliar with modern technology. They remain untouched by the global trends and cultural changes, but the young generation on behalf of their modern education and orientation with the technology remains in contact with the global trends, and these trends influence their minds and thoughts, which are usually reflected in their daily actions and interactions within the family and outside, which as a result creates a gap between the two age groups, that later converted in conflicts and distress.

Knowledge and Understanding of Generation Gap of the Old Generation

In this part of the study, the respondents were asked about their knowledge and understating of the generation gap. They were asked about their insight and experience in the terms of this generational conflict. Additionally, they explored their thinking and ideas about generational discrepancies. In the same way, they were investigated regarding their views about the generation gap in the terms of joint family and the nuclear family. Besides this, the respondents were inquired about their suffering as well as the young generation from this gap. In addition to this, the respondents were asked about changes that occurred in familial life and the causes and factors that promote the generation gap. The following table shows the responses of the respondents.

S.#	Statements	SA f& %	A f& %	NO f& %	DA f& %	SDA f& %
1	The generation gap exists in my society.	(161) 80.5%	(39) 19.5%	(0) 0%	(0) 0%	(0) 0%
2	The old generation suffers more from the generation gap	(137) 68.5%	(62) 31%	(0) 0%	(1) .5%	(0) 0%
3	The young generation suffers more from the generation gap	(32) 16.0%	(125) 62.5%	(1) .5%	(40) 20%	(2) 1%
4	Generation gap exists more in joint families	(151) 75.5%	(47) 23.5%	(0) 0%	(2) 1%	(0) 0%
5	The generation gap exists more in nuclear families	(34) 17%	(119) 59.5%	(4) 2%	(41) 20.5%	(2) 1%
6	Generation gap influenced dress and food pattern	(124) 62%	(73) 36.5%	(0) 0%	(3) 1.5%	(0) 0%
7	The generation gap is caused due to social change	(128) 64%	(66) 33%	(1) .5%	(4) 2%	(1) .5%
8	The generation gap is caused due to technology	(153) 76.5%	(45) 22.5%	(2) 1%	(0) 0%	(0) 0%
9	The generation gap is caused due to education	(66) 33%	(81) 40.5%	(1) .5%	(41) 20.5%	(11) 5.5%

Table elaborates the data about the knowledge and understanding of the respondents of this

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study. For this purpose, various questions were asked from the respondents in which they documented their views regarding these questions. In this respect, 80.5 % of the respondents strongly agree with the statement that a generation gap existed in their society. Moreover, 19.5% of the respondents agreed with the statement that a generation gap existed in their community. The above percentage indicates that all the respondents reported that the generation gap existed in their society.

The table further explains the data that the old generation suffers more from the generation gap. Regarding this question, 68.5% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that the old generation suffers more in terms of the generation gap. Moreover, 31% of the respondents also agreed with the statement while only 0.5% of the respondents disagreed that the old generation does not suffer from the generation gap.

The table moreover depicts the data that the young generation also suffers more from the generation gap. From this perspective, 62.5% of the respondents agreed with the statement that the young generation also suffers more from the generation gap. However, 20% of the respondents disagreed with the statement that the young generation suffers more from the generation gap. Nevertheless, 16% of the respondents strongly agree with the statement that the young generation suffers more from the generation gap. In addition to this, 1% of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement that the young generation suffers more from the generation gap. Only .5% of the respondents marked the no opinion option.

The table describes further the data that the generation gap exists more in joint families. In this regard, 75.5% of the respondents strongly agree with the statement that the generation gap exists more in joint families. Moreover, 23.5% of the respondents were found to agree with the statement that the generation gap exists more in joint families, however, 1% of the respondents disagreed with the statement and replied that the generation gap does not exist more in joint families.

Table further documents data that the generation gap exists more in nuclear families. Responding to this question 59.5% of the respondents answered that they agree with the statement that the generation gap exists more in nuclear families. However, 20.5% of the respondents disagreed with the statement and expressed that the generation gap does not exist more in nuclear families. But on the contradiction, 17% of the respondents strongly agree with the statement. Besides this 2% of the respondent neither agree nor disagree with the statement and only 1% of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement.

The table moreover elaborates on the data that the generation gap influenced the dress and food patterns. In this respect, 62% of the respondents strongly agree with the statement that the generation gap influenced the dress and food patterns. In addition to this, 36.5% of the respondents agreed with the same statement that the generation gap influenced the food and dress pattern, however, only 1.5% of the respondents disagreed with the statement and replied that the generation gap has not influenced the dress and food patterns.

The table explains further the data that the generation gap is caused due to social change. Replying to this question 64% of the respondents were found strongly agree with the statement that the generation gap is caused due to social change. Further, 33% of the respondents agreed with the statement that the generation gap is caused due to social change. But, 2% of the respondents disagreed with the statement. Moreover, 0.5% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement and in the same way, 0.5% of the respondents neither

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agree nor disagree with the statement.

The table moreover reveals the data that the generation gap is caused due to technology. So, in this context, 76.5% of the respondents strongly agree with the statement that the generation gap is caused due to technology. Additionally, 22.5% of the respondents agreed with the statement that the generation gap is caused due to technology, however, only 1% of the respondents marked the no opinion option.

The table at the end depicts the data that the generation gap is caused due to education. Answering this question 40.5% of the respondents agreed with the statement that the generation gap is caused due to education. Moreover, 33% of the respondents strongly agree with the statement that education is causing a generation gap. However, 20.5% of the respondents disagreed with the statement, similarly, 5.5% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement that the generation gap is caused due to education. Only 0.5% of the respondents marked neither agree nor disagree regarding the statement.

Actions and Interactions: Old Generation’s Behavior towards Young Generation

Actions and interactions are characterized by the impact of meanings and symbols. This scheme claims that social relations, norms, values, and customs are the outcome of social activities and interactions. It further explains that socialization is an internalizing process given through actions and interactions of the family and other members of society. In the process of social interaction people symbolically communicate meanings to the others involved. The others interpret those symbols and orient their responding action based on their interpretation. In other words, in social interaction, the actor engages in a process of mutual influence. In this portion of the study, the respondents will be asked about the actions and interactions within the family and their behavior towards children. They were asked about their interaction with the young members of the family. They were examined in the terms of cooperation and support from the young members of the family. Similarly, the respondents were investigated about their children's socialization. Besides this, they were asked about children's expenditures and the importance given to their opinions within the family. Moreover, the respondents' inquiry regarding their secrets and privacies sharing with their children. The following table explains the replies of the respondents.

S.#	Statements	SA f & %	A f & %	NO f & %	DA f & %	SDA f & %
1	The behavior of the young generation is not cooperative in daily life	(92) 46%	(80) 40%	(1) .5%	(26) 13%	(1) .5%
2	The old generation is not obedient/supportive in everyday interaction	(0) 0%	(39) 19.5%	(0) 0%	(82) 41%	(79) 39.5%
3	Youth most of the time remain in distance from elders in everyday life	(95) 47.5%	(88) 44%	(1) .5%	(16) 8%	(0) 0%
4	The traditional childcare method creates a gap between the old and young generation	(4) 2%	(58) 29%	(1) .5%	(91) 45.5%	(46) 23%
5	The old generation socialize their young sons in term of making them sub-	(26) 13%	(86) 43%	(0) 0%	(74) 37%	(14) 7%

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	ordinate and submissive					
6	The old generation believes that youth are not able to be part of routine decisions made within the family	(34) 17%	(67) 33.5%	(0) 0%	(85) 42.5%	(14) 7%
7	The elders often neglect the opinion of the young generation in family	(46) 23%	(83) 41.5%	(0) 0%	(57) 28.5%	(14) 7%
8	The old generation is careless regarding the expenditures of the young members of the family	(4) 2%	(71) 35.5%	(0) 0%	(81) 40.5%	(44) 22%
9	The old generation does not confidently share secrecies/privacies with the young generation	(88) 44%	(77) 38.5%	(0) 0%	(34) 17%	(1) .5%

The table elucidates data about the views of the respondents regarding their actions and interactions within the family and parents' behavior towards children. In this respect, different questions were asked from the respondents in which they shared their views regarding these questions. In this context, 46% of the respondents strongly agree with the statement that the behavior of the young generation is not cooperative in daily life. In the same way, 40% of the respondents agreed with the same statement that the behavior of the young generation is not cooperative in daily life. However, 13% of the respondents disagreed with the statement, besides this 0.5% of the respondents were strongly disagree with the statement, and with the same percent means 0.5% of the respondents replied with the no opinion option.

The table further explains data about the statement that the old generation is not obedient/supportive in everyday interaction. Regarding this question, 41% of the respondents disagreed with the statement that the old generation is not obedient/supportive in everyday interaction. In addition to this 39.5% of the respondents strongly disagree with the statement, however, 19.5% of the respondents responded that they agree with the statement.

The table moreover describes data that youth most of the time remain a distance from elders in everyday life. In this respect, 47.5% of the respondents strongly agree with the statement that youth most of the time remain at a distance from elders in everyday life. Besides this 44% of the respondents were agree with the statement, however, 8% of the respondents disagreed with the statement, and only 0.5% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree with the statement.

Table further documents data that the traditional childcare method creates a gap between the old and young generations. In this perspective, 45.5% of the respondents disagreed with the statement that the traditional childcare method creates a gap between the old and young generation, but on the other side, 29% of the respondents agreed with the statement. However, 23% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement, but 2% of the respondents strongly agree with the statement and only 0.5% of the respondents were of no opinion regarding the statement.

The table depicts further data that the old generation socializes their young sons in terms of making them subordinate and submissive. Responding to this question 43% of the respondents agreed with the statement that the old generation socializes their young sons in

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the term of making them subordinate and submissive. But 37% of the respondents were found to disagree with the statement, however, 13% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement. Nonetheless, 7% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement.

The table explains further data that the old generation believes that youth are not able to be part of routine decisions made within the family. So, in this respect, 42.5% of the respondents disagreed with the statement that the old generation believes that youth are not able to be part of routine decisions made within the family. However, 33.5% of the respondents agreed with the statement, moreover, 17% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement and in contradiction, 7% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement.

The table further elaborates data that the elders often neglect the opinion of the young generation in the family. Replying to this question 41.5% of the respondents answered that they agree with the statement that the elders neglect the opinion of the young generation in the family. Nevertheless, 28.5% of the respondents disagreed with the statement. But 23% of the respondents strongly agree with the statement and 7% of the respondents on the other side strongly disagree with the statement.

The table illuminates further data that the old generation is careless regarding the expenditures of the young members of the family. In this context, 40.5% of the respondents disagreed with the statement that the old generation is careless regarding the expenditures of the young members of the family. However, 35.5% of the respondents agreed with the statement, moreover, 22% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement and 2% of the respondents strongly agree with the statement.

The table at the end indicates that the old generation does not confidently share secrecies/privacies with the young generation. Responding to this question 44% of the respondents shared that they strongly agree with the statement that the old generation does not confidently share secrecies/privacies with the young generation. In the same way, 38.5% of the respondents agreed with the statement, nevertheless, 17% of the respondents disagreed with the statement while only 0.5% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the statement.

Relationship between variables regarding the generation gap

Correlation between the variables		The old generation suffers more
Social change causes a generation gap	Pearson Correlation	.147*
	N	200
		The old generation suffers more
Technology causes a generation gap	Pearson Correlation	.201**
	N	200
		Lack of trust building
Old generation neglect young	Pearson Correlation	.438**
	N	200

* and **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 and 0.001 levels (2-tailed).

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The table depicts that social change had a significant positive correlation with the old generation suffering from a generation gap (0.147*), technology had a significant positive correlation with the old generation suffering from a generation gap (0.201**), and the old generation neglected the young generation had a significant positive correlation with lack of trust building between the young generation and old generation (0.438**). In this regard, wherever social change took place in the same way generation gap was also increasing. Moreover, technology was another factor in the generation gap. In this regard generation gap was increasing with technological development. Furthermore, the old generation neglected the young generation which led the young generation to distance from the old generation. All the variables show a positive relationship. It indicates that the generation gap is increasing with the social change, technological development, and the negligence of the young generation by the old generation in terms of not accepting the existence and capability of the young generation. Therefore, the generation gap becomes a real-world phenomenon.

Discussions

The generation gap exists everywhere in the world, but it usually exists more in those societies where the people live a joint family life, are less literate, and are more unfamiliar with technology. In this research study, all the respondents agreed that a generation gap exists in their community. The young and the old generations are of different opinions regarding life experiences and different in their thoughts. The respondents agreed that this gap has suffered more than the old generation. It is because the old generation is uneducated or less educated. They are unfamiliar with the modern tools and technology, and the young generation more often engages with these tools, besides this, parents are dependent on their children, and their freedom is restricted, which ultimately promotes the ideas gap. The respondents were also agreeing in the majority that this gap has also suffered more than the children. Because when there are discrepancies in the two age groups, so, it affects a single age group or generation but there will be an influence on either group. The young generation wants freedom and private life, and the old generation doesn't let them out of their control. So, as a result the young generation also faces difficulties. In the research study, it was agreed that the generation gap exists more in joint families. because in joint families there is always disharmony and diverse opinions regarding familial issues, which ultimately produce a generation gap. In the same way, it was also observed that generational differences exist in nuclear families however, with the low magnitude than the joint families, it is because the young generation is going to adopt modern trends and the old generation usually denounce and bar them to do so.

In the research study, it was investigated that the generation gap has influenced dress and food patterns. It is an undeniable fact that what a person learns will reflect in his practice, so, in this way the young generation always learns from the global trends and subsequently apply these techniques in their social and familial life. During the study, it was noted the majority of the respondents were of the view that social change has geared up the generation gap. It is said when there are cultural and normative changes, there must be social change. Rapid globalization, urbanization, and cultural hybridization have changed and changed very rapidly in every society in the world. So, it can be said that social change is one of the causes of the generation gap, besides this, almost all the respondents found agreed that technology

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is a factor that leads society towards generational differences. It is indeed a common fact that technology has diverted the young generation towards social isolation, but the parents want to remain in frequent contact with their children to share daily life activities and experiences. So, in this way technology is the factor that enhances the generation gap between the two age groups. In the study, it was inquired that education is also a factor that increases the generation gap. The majority of the respondents agreed that the education of children has distanced them from their parents regarding views and ideas mismatch. Through education and awareness, the young generation has changed their behavior and attitudes, which are in no sense in line with the conservative narrative ultimately causing the gap between the two generations.

Actions and interactions have a vital role in personality development and social life. Through the interaction, the individuals communicate and exchange their views and ideas with each other. So, examining the influence of interaction within the family majority of the respondents complained that the behavior of the young generation is not cooperative in daily life. The youth has found often spending more time out of the home. The parents indeed need support at this age regarding their health and socio-economic needs, but the children avoid helping them out. In the study, it was understood that the old generation is supportive of everyday interaction. The majority of the respondents disagreed that they are not supportive of their children. They argue that they have supported them at the expense of their youth. They have fulfilled all their demands. The study further investigated that the respondents in the majority confessed that youth are not given time and remain at a distance from them. It is because of the different life priorities of the two generations. The two age groups think differently, which ultimately disintegrates them from each other. The study explored that majority of the respondents disagreed the traditional childcare method creates a gap between the two generations. Regarding this statement, the parents always argue that they are thinking for their children's betterment, if they scold or sometimes beat them that is in their interest. In the same way, the study inquired about the old generation socializing their children to make them submissive and sub-ordinate. The respondents were approximately divided into two halves regarding this statement. because there is variation regarding their mentality, proximity to urban areas, and education, some parents must think to make their children submissive, while others handle them in an independent atmosphere.

During the study, it was found that the respondents were divided almost into two halves to believe that the young generation may not be part of routine decisions made in the family. the parents often think that their children are not that mature to share and involve them in the family decisions. They think that cannot give some valuable inputs to give a bright result. So, they consider that it is better to keep them aside during the decisions made in the family, however, there is half the population that gives importance to the views of youth and includes them in family decisions. In the study, it was assessed that the majority of the respondents agreed that the elders neglect the opinion of the young generation in the family. It is because the parents think and says that the young generation is careless and emotional. Their future sight is very short. They don't think about the repercussions of some decisions and handle things emotionally. In the study, the respondents in the majority disagreed that the old generation is careless regarding the expenditure of young members of the family. they usually share that too much money betrays the young members because at this stage they are quite

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mature to decide well and spend money on some beneficial work, but waisted them in nefarious activities. They consider it a check and balance on the young generation. During the investigation, it was understood that the majority of the respondents agreed that the old generation does not share secrets and privacies with the young generation. They are not confident about the young generation. They think it will cause harm if secrets were shared with the young members.

Conclusions

The cleavage that occurred between the two generations regarding their ideas mismatch and life experiences is termed the generation gap. This gap of ideas and thoughts is conscious as well as unconscious, however, consequently harms relations between the old generation and the young generation, which later converted into conflict. The generational gap usually exists more in societies that are passing through the transitional period and social change. The young generation moving forward with the demands and trends of the modern world and the old generation remains and tries to be stuck to their traditional trends, which as a result disturb the familial, social, and emotional life of both generations. This research study was conducted to assess the knowledge and understanding of respondents about the generation gap and the impressions of actions and interactions that cause the generation gap among the Pashtun parents in Balochistan. The study was based upon the quantitative research method, in which the data was collected from three districts of the Zhob division, including Zhob, Killa Saifullah, and Loralai through a proportionate random sampling technique. The elements/respondents for the data were the old generations having ages above fifty years. The sample size for the study was 200 male respondents, and the data was collected from these respondents through a structured interview schedule. Regarding the generation gap, the respondents believed that a generation gap exists in their community, which suffers both generations. They further communicated that this gap is found in both types of families, the joint and nuclear family, however, its intensity is high in joint families. They further agreed that the generation gap has influenced domestic life regarding food and dressing patterns. The study explored that technology, society, and education are the factors that widen the gap between the two age groups. It was further examined that the old generation complained that the young generation is not cooperating and supporting them in daily life and viewed that youth often remained in distance from them. They disagreed to share privacies with the young generation and expressed that they are supportive of their young children and do what they consider best for them.

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